

Quantum Bound Densities

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In a previous note (1), we argued that in quantum bound states, the classical potential $V(x)$ is really an average i.e. equal to $\text{Sum over } k V(k) \exp(ikx)$. Mathematically, this is the well-known Fourier series, but in this note we try to argue there are important physical implications which lead to the hump like densities in numerous cases in quantum mechanics, unlike what is found in the classical case. In addition, we argue that the stochastic potential creates a momentum distribution at x which may be used to calculate average kinetic energy (at x). Because average kinetic energy changes with x , the momentum distribution must also change. At a given x , summing $P(p/x)$ accounts for all possible momentum states and yields $W(x)$, the wavefunction. Because this differs with x , the probability $P(x)$ must differ with x as well, yielding a quantum density not seen in classical physics. Thus, quantum bound state density is due to the spatial change in momentum distribution probabilities with x , we argue.

Quantum Stochastic Potential

We argue that $V(x)$ in quantum bound systems is an average of $\text{Sum over } k V(k)\exp(ikx)$. Mathematically, this a Fourier series, but we argue it has important physical implications in terms of creating quantum densities with humps. We note that if $V(k)=V(-k)$, there are terms of the form $V(k)2\cos(kx)$ which means that for certain regions of x near zeros of $\cos(kx)$, the potential is almost zero. Similar considerations hold for the force. We argue that a stochastic force term yields a momentum hit of k or $-k$, so for some regions such a $k/-k$ hit may not be rendered. Furthermore, these regions are periodic (due to $\cos(kx)$). Thus, it is not only the case that at a given time t and point x , one is unsure of which $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ renders a hit, but given knowledge about x , certain k hits may not occur at all or with very low probability. Thus, there is a spatially periodic pattern for each $k/-k$ momentum hit. If $\cos(kx)$ becomes negative, we argue momentum hits are in the opposite direction of the average force $-dV(x)/dx$. In other words, stochastic hits of $k/-k$ are in one direction and then the other with regions of almost no $k/-k$ hit between the two. It seems as if the stochastic potential $V(k)\cos(kx)$ is trying to knock the particle back and forth (relative to the average force $-dV/dx$) and almost disappearing in space between different directional hits.

This spatial periodicity affects momentum distributions. We have argued in (1) that due to the stochastic potential, a momentum distribution is created at each point x , namely $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x)$ the wavefunction is a normalization constant and $P(p/x)$ a conditional probability. In this note, we point out that spatial periodicity present in the stochastic potential term $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ carries over into the conditional momentum probability. Thus, if $a(p)=a(-p)$, then $P(p/x)$ contains terms such as $a(p)2\cos(px)$ (for the combination of $-p/p$) which becomes small at periodic x positions. In other words, particular $p/-p$ momentum values are almost absent from the distribution at periodic x positions.

Density and the Quantum Potential

In classical physics, density is defined as the number of particles in a certain volume. This idea carries over into classical statistical mechanics. In a single particle quantum bound state, there is only one particle so one is really concerned with the probability to find the particle in one dx region versus another. Matters are complicated further if one considers quantum mechanics to be a statistical theory with a distribution of momentum states (at different times) at the same x , similar in a sense to classical statistical mechanics. In classical statistical mechanics, however, two body collisions are the driver whereas we argue that $V(x)$, the potential, is the driver in the quantum picture. We have argued that it leads to a conditional probability of $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ at each x . The average kinetic energy at each x satisfies:

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} p^2/2m a(p)\exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The average kinetic energy, given by the first term of ((1)), changes with x , so the momentum distribution must change also. Thus, at a given x , one may compare $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x)$ with $a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$ i.e. the relative probabilities of two momenta. Summing relative probabilities yields $W(x)$, thus there is not simply a momentum distribution at each x , but different summed probabilities between one x and another. This suggests there is a different probability for the particle to be at one x versus another simply based on momentum probabilities and their x dependence.

An immediate question is: Why isn't $W(x)$ the spatial density? It is the sum of relative conditional probability values, so it is a measure of probability at x . We argue that spatial density must depend on an interval dx and not on a point. At a point x , the relative conditional probability is $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which changes to $a(p)\exp(ip(x+dx))$ at $x+dx$. Thus, we argue that a stochastic collision occurs with the stochastic potential in order to change the momentum distribution. On average, these collisions equal the average work done as shown in (2). In a small interval dx , one is interested in two momentum values, the initial and the new one after the collision. Thus, the probability in question is $a(p_i)\exp(ip_i x) a(p_j)\exp(ip_j x)$. If one sums over i and j and then integrates over x one obtains 1, so this is a probability, strictly related to momenta. Nevertheless, because it changes from one x to another and summing over i and j yields also possible combinations, the sum represents a probability based on x . Different summed momentum probabilities at different x values suggest different $P(x)$. So: $P(x) = \sum_{i,j} a(p_i)\exp(ip_i x) a(p_j)\exp(ip_j x)$.

Earlier, we asked why $W(x)$ was not spatial density. Even though it is not, it still plays an important role. For example, consider the average:

$$\sum_{\text{over } p} f(p) P(p/x) P(x) = \left[\sum_{\text{over } p} f(p) a(p)\exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) \quad \text{where } f(p) \text{ is a function of } p \quad ((2))$$

The term in $\langle \dots \rangle$ is the relative average at x , so $f(p)$ averages occur with only one $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ term i.e. $\sum_{i,j} f(p_i)a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix) a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx)$.

Implications of Quantum Density

Quantum spatial density is of the form: $\sum_{i,j} a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix) a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx) = W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state. $W(x)$, however, is an ensemble average. We argue that at a given time t_1 , a particle is at x and has a probability $P(p/x)$ to have momentum p . One may write the spatial density as: $\sum_{i,j} a(p_i)a(p_j) \exp(i(p_i+p_j)x)$. It may be noted that the particle does not have a physical momentum of p_i+p_j . At x it has p_i and then between x and $x+dx$ it changes to p_j . Nevertheless, the product probability contains spatial periodicity based on $\exp(i(p_i+p_j)x)$ and it is this product momentum probability which determines spatial probability. If $a(p)=a(-p)$, one has terms of the form $a(p_i)a(p_j)2\cos((p_i+p_j)x)$ which may be positive, negative or very small. It should be noted such behaviour follows for all i,j combinations for which $p_i+p_j=p$ i.e. one has $[\sum_{p_i+p_j=p} a(p_i)a(p_j)2] \cos((p_i+p_j)x)$. For certain regions, this term becomes negative and lowers overall density while in other regions, it is very low because one is near x values for which $\cos((p_i+p_j)x)=0$. The physical periodicity originates with $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ which in turn follows from the stochastic potential. The spatial density spatial periodicity follows from the physical periodicity of the two factors $a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix)$ and $a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx)$.

In a previous note, we argued that an average force $-dV/dx$ may point in one direction, but that a stochastic term $V(k)\exp(ikx)$ may render a force in the opposite. Likewise, $a(p)2\cos(px)$ may be negative in a certain region indicating that the particle is moving opposite to the average flow and so in a sense contributing a negative contribution (say to average p or $p^*p/2m$). For the product probabilities of spatial density, average values of a function of p , $f(p)$, are still based on only one $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Thus, one may consider $\sum_{j} a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix) a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx) = a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix) W(x)$ and then use the idea of $\text{Re}(a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix))<0$ as indicating opposite directional flow, as argued in a previous note.

Density Humps

In the previous sections, it was noted that $p/-p$ components of $P(p/x)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ yield $2a(p)\cos(px)$ terms which are periodic. The higher p , the smaller the wavelength. This may be considered in a different manner, namely $p^*p \cos(px) = -d/dx d/dx \cos(px)$. Thus, the higher the curvature, the higher the frequency of $\cos(px)$. $P(p/x)$ is a combination of many different $\cos(px)$ terms, but average kinetic energy as in ((1)) is of the form $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W / W$ which is the same form as: $-d/dx d/dx \cos(px)$. Thus, for a higher average kinetic energy values, one expects more humps in $W(x)$ similar to that of $\cos(px)$. In other words, microscopic periodicity in the $\cos(px)$ terms may lead to an overall macroscopic spatial periodicity. This appears in both the cases of a particle in a box with infinite walls and the harmonic oscillator. Increasing energy with $V(x)$ remaining unchanged means average kinetic energy must increase in ((1)). One way for this to happen is to have steeper humps in $W(x)$ which lead to steeper humps in $W(x)W(x)$. Given that $W(x) = \sum_{p} 2a(p) \cos(px)$ for $a(p)=a(-p)$, this means that weights $a(p)$ are

such that they mimic a particular frequency wave. In the case of the particle in a box (infinite potential at the walls), the mimicry is exact - a macroscopic sinusoidal form is produced by having a $a(p)$ peak at p_{ave} . In particular, even though all p_i 's are excited for a particle in a box with infinite walls (see (3)), because kinetic energy does not change with x , a $p_i = \pm p_{ave}$ which has a spatial probability of $2a(p)\cos(p_{ave} x)$ caused by the stochastic force (i.e. moving backwards and forwards) even though on average there is no force except at the walls. $P(p/x) = p_{ave}$ for all x , so:

$$\sum_p a(p) \cos(px) / W(x) \approx a(p_{ave}) \cos(p_{ave} x) / W(x) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{so } W(x) \approx \cos(p_{ave} x)$$

Thus, $W(x)$ really follows the forward/backward probability motion of the microscopic $\cos(p_{ave} x)$. For the oscillator, matters are more complicated, but more and more humps appear as the energy is raised.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a stochastic potential which only equals $V(x)$ on average (i.e. $V(x) = \sum_k a(k) \exp(ikx)$), creates a momentum distribution at each x . Averages using this distribution may be used to calculate average kinetic energy at x for example. Because ave KE changes with x , the momentum distribution must also change with x . Given a point x , however, a particle must be in one or another momentum state, each with probability $P(p_i/x)$. Adding all of these yields $W(x)$, but this differs from point to point. Thus, it seems one must conclude that $P(x)$ differs from point to point. Thus, quantum density is due to the sum of $P(p_i/x)$ changing with x i.e. to $W(x)$ the wavefunction changing with x . It is the probability of the dynamics which changes with x and creates a quantum spatial density. $W(x)$, however, cannot be spatial density because it exists at a point and is not related to an interval dx . A given $a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix)$, however, changes to $a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx)$ within dx so combinations: $a(p_i)\exp(ip_ix)a(p_j)\exp(ip_jx)$ summed over i and j yield a probability spatial density.

For a given p and $a(p) = a(-p)$, $W(x)$ contains $2a(p)\cos(px)$ terms. The higher p , the higher the frequency, but $-d/dx d/dx \cos(px) = p^2 \cos(px)$, so the higher the kinetic energy of a term, the higher the frequency. p^2 is the curvature of the function $\cos(px)$ and a high p means many humps. The form of the ensemble average of KE, however, is the same, i.e. $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W/W$ so one may argue that as E (energy) increases, the curvature increases and there should be more and steeper humps. This occurs for a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls and for the harmonic oscillator.

References

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